

Appendix 2: List of spider taxa that I described/co-described based on material from Iran, either in part or in whole. The known distributions are mentioned in brackets, with type localities of species underlined.

Genera

Asiascape Zamani & Marusik, 2020 (Agelenidae) [Iran]

Bastanius Mirshamsi, Zamani & Marusik, 2016 (Hersiliidae) [Iran]

Bosselaerius Zamani & Marusik, 2020 (Phrurolithidae) [Azerbaijan, Iran, Tajikistan, China]

Callipelis Zamani & Marusik, 2017 (Gnaphosidae) [Iran]

Ecurobius Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Amaurobiidae) [Iran]

Iranotricha Zamani & Marusik, 2018 (Gnaphosidae) [Iran]

Kharitonovia Esyunin, Zamani & Tuneva, 2017 (Dictynidae) [Iran, Uzbekistan]

Persilena Zamani & Marusik, 2020 (Agelenidae) [Iran]

Persiscape Zamani & Marusik, 2020 (Agelenidae) [Lesbos, Israel, Turkey, Georgia, Azerbaijan, Iran]

Sestakovaia Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Liocranidae) [Central Europe, Near East, northern Iran]

Zagrotus Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021 (Gnaphosidae) [Iran]

Species

Acanthinozodium armita Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Zodariidae) [Iran]

Acanthinozodium atrisa Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Zodariidae) [Iran]

Acanthinozodium diara Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Zodariidae) [Iran]

Acanthinozodium dorsa Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Zodariidae) [Iran]

Acanthinozodium elburzicum Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Zodariidae) [Iran]

Acanthinozodium kiana Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Zodariidae) [Iran]

Acanthinozodium masa Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Zodariidae) [Iran]

Acanthinozodium niusha Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Zodariidae) [Iran]

Acanthinozodium parmida Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Zodariidae) [Iran]

Acanthinozodium parysatis Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Zodariidae) [Iran]

Acanthinozodium sorani Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Zodariidae) [Iran]

Aelurillus westi Azarkina & Zamani, 2019 (Salticidae) [Iran]

Agroeca angirasu Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Liocranidae) [Iran]

Aituaria iranica Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Nesticidae) [Iran]

Ajmonia rajaeii Zamani & Marusik, 2017 (Dictynidae) [Iran]

Alopecosa murphyorum Zamani, Nadolny, Esyunin & Marusik, 2022 (Lycosidae) [Iran]

Alopecosa robertsi Zamani, Nadolny, Esyunin & Marusik, 2022 (Lycosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Anemesia kopenhageni Marusik, Zamani & Mirshamsi, 2014 (Cyrtoucheniidae) [[Iran](#)]

Araniella mithra Zamani, Marusik & Šestáková, 2020 (Araneidae) [[Iran](#)]

Araniella villanii Zamani, Marusik & Šestáková, 2020 (Araneidae) [[Iran](#), Kazakhstan, India]

Asiascape parthica Zamani & Marusik, 2020 (Agelenidae) [[Iran](#)]

Azerithonica sagartia Zamani & Marusik, 2019 (Agelenidae) [[Iran](#)]

Bastanius kermanensis Mirshamsi, Zamani & Marusik, 2016 (Hersiliidae) [[Iran](#)]

Berinda hoerwegi Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021 (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Berlandina artaxerxes Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021 (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Bosselaerius hyrcanicus Zamani & Marusik, 2020 (Phrurolithidae) [[Azerbaijan](#), Iran]

Brigittea avicenna Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Dictynidae) [[Iran](#)]

Callipelis deserticola Zamani & Marusik, 2017 (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Cebrennus rambodjavani Moradmand, Zamani & Jäger, 2016 (Sparassidae) [[Iran](#)]

Cheiracanthium iranicum Esyunin & Zamani, 2020 (Cheiracanthiidae) [[Iran](#)]

Cryptodrassus iranicus Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021 (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Deltshevia taftanensis Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Hersiliidae) [[Iran](#)]

Devade naderii Zamani & Marusik, 2017 (Dictynidae) [[Iran](#)]

Diaea osmanii Zamani & Marusik, 2017 (Thomisidae) [[Iran](#)]

Drassodes marusiki Esyunin & Zamani, 2019 (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Drassodes persianus Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021 (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Duninia grodnitskyi Zamani & Marusik, 2018 (Hersiliidae) [[Iran](#)]

Dysdera achaemenes Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023 (Dysderidae) [[Iran](#)]

Dysdera bakhtiari Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023 (Dysderidae) [[Iran](#)]

Dysdera damavandica Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023 (Dysderidae) [[Iran](#)]

Dysdera genoensis Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023 (Dysderidae) [[Iran](#)]

Dysdera hormuzensis Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023 (Dysderidae) [[Iran](#)]

Dysdera iranica Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023 (Dysderidae) [[Iran](#)]

Dysdera isfahanica Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023 (Dysderidae) [[Iran](#)]

Dysdera mazeruni Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023 (Dysderidae) [[Iran](#)]

Dysdera medes Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023 (Dysderidae) [[Iran](#)]

Dysdera persica Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023 (Dysderidae) [[Iran](#)]

Dysdera sagartia Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023 (Dysderidae) [[Iran](#)]

Dysdera tapuria Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023 (Dysderidae) [[Iran](#)]

Dysdera verkana Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023 (Dysderidae) [[Iran](#)]

Dysdera xerxesi Zamani, Marusik & Szűts, 2023 (Dysderidae) [[Iran](#)]

Echemus caspicus Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021 (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Eucrobius parthicus Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Amaurobiidae) [[Iran](#)]

Episinus mikhailovi Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Theridiidae) [[Iran](#)]

Eresus adaleari Zamani & Szűts, 2020 (Eresidae) [[Iran](#)]

Euryopsis schwendingeri Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Theridiidae) [[Iran](#)]

Evarcha dena Zamani, 2017 (Salticidae) [[Iran](#)]

Filistata balouchi Zamani & Marusik, 2020 (Filistatidae) [[Iran](#)]

Filistata maguirei Marusik & Zamani, 2015 (Filistatidae) [[Iran](#)]

Gnaphosa qamsarica Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021 (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Hahnia deiocesi Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Hahniidae) [[Iran](#)]

Haplodrassus medes Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021 (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Haplodrassus qashqai Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021 (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Hersilia talebii Mirshamsi, Zamani & Marusik, 2016 (Hersiliidae) [[Iran](#)]

Hersiliola artemisiae Zamani, Mirshamsi & Marusik, 2017 (Hersiliidae) [[Iran](#)]

Iranotricha lutensis Zamani & Marusik, 2018 (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Ischnocolus vanandelae Montemor, West & Zamani, 2020 (Theraphosidae) [[Iran](#), [Oman](#)]

Lachesana kavirensis Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Zodariidae) [[Iran](#)]

Lachesana perseus Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Zodariidae) [[Iran](#)]

Levymanus dezfulensis Zamani & Marusik, 2020 (Palpimanidae) [[Iran](#)]

Loureedia phoenixi Zamani & Marusik, 2020 (Eresidae) [[Iran](#)]

Loxosceles coheni Zamani, Mirshamsi & Marusik, 2021 (Sicariidae) [[Iran](#)]

Loxosceles persica Ribera & Zamani, 2017 (Sicariidae) [[Iran](#)]

Loxosceles turanensis Zamani, Mirshamsi & Marusik, 2021 (Sicariidae) [[Iran](#), [Turkmenistan](#)]

Lycosa aragogi Nadolny & Zamani, 2017 (Lycosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Lycosa elymaisa Zamani & Nadolny, 2022 (Lycosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Lycosa macrophthalma Nadolny & Zamani, 2020 (Lycosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Marinarozelotes achaemenes Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021 (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Marjanus isfahanicus Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021 (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Mesiotelus caucasicus Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Liocranidae) [Turkey, Armenia, [Azerbaijan](#), Iran]

Mesiotelus patricki Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Liocranidae) [[Iran](#)]

Micaria atropatene Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Microfilistata magalhaesi Zamani & Marusik, 2018 (Filistatidae) [[Iran](#)]

Neoscona isatis Zamani, Marusik & Šestáková, 2020 (Araneidae) [[Iran](#)]

Nomisia ameretatae Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021 (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Oecobius fahimii Zamani & Marusik, 2018 (Oecobiidae) [[Iran](#)]

Oecobius ferdowsii Mirshamsi, Zamani & Marusik, 2017 (Oecobiidae) [[Iran](#), Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan]

Oecobius ilamensis Zamani, Mirshamsi & Marusik, 2017 (Oecobiidae) [[Iran](#)]

Palpimanus carmania Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Palpimanidae) [[Iran](#)]

Palpimanus persicus Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Palpimanidae) [[Iran](#)]

Paracedicus kasatkini Zamani & Marusik, 2017 (Cybaeidae) [[Iran](#)]

Paratheuma enigmatica Zamani, Marusik & Berry, 2016 (Dictynidae) [[Iran](#)]

Pardosa zagrosica Zamani & Nadolny, 2022 (Lycosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Pax ellipita Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Zodariidae) [[Iran](#)]

Pax leila Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Zodariidae) [[Iran](#)]

Persilena sengleti Zamani & Marusik, 2020 (Agelenidae) [[Iran](#)]

Persiscape caspica Zamani & Marusik, 2020 (Agelenidae) [[Iran](#)]

Persiscape ecbatana Zamani & Marusik, 2020 (Agelenidae) [[Iran](#)]

Persiscape nassirkhanii Zamani & Marusik, 2020 (Agelenidae) [[Iran](#)]

Persiscape zagrosensis Zamani & Marusik, 2020 (Agelenidae) [[Iran](#)]

Phrurolithus azarkinae Zamani & Marusik, 2020 (Phrurolithidae) [Cyprus, Turkey, Armenia, [Azerbaijan](#), Iran]

Phyxioschema gedrosia Schwendinger & Zamani, 2018 (Euagridae) [[Iran](#)]

Piratula raika Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Lycosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Pritha garfieldi Marusik & Zamani, 2015 (Filistatidae) [[Iran](#)]

Prodidomus inexpectatus Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021 (Prodidomidae) [[Iran](#)]

Proszynskiana izadii Azarkina & Zamani, 2019 (Salticidae) [[Iran](#)]

Proszynskiana logunovi Azarkina & Zamani, 2019 (Salticidae) [[Iran](#)]

Pseudomicrommata mokranica Moradmand, Zamani & Jäger, 2019 (Sparassidae) [[Iran](#)]

Pterotricha kovblyuki Zamani & Marusik, 2018 (Gnaphosidae) [Iraq, [Iran](#), UAE]

Pterotricha montana Zamani & Marusik, 2018 (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Raveniola mazandarana Marusik, Zamani & Mirshamsi, 2014 (Nemesiidae) [[Iran](#)]

Rhysodromus genoensis Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Philodromidae) [[Iran](#)]

Rhysodromus medes Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Philodromidae) [[Iran](#)]

Sahastata amethystina Marusik & Zamani, 2016 (Filistatidae) [[Iran](#)]

Sahastata sinuspersica Marusik, Zamani & Mirshamsi, 2014 (Filistatidae) [[Iran](#), Pakistan, India]

Salticus lucasi Zamani, Hosseini & Moradmand, 2020 (Salticidae) [[Iran](#)]

Scotophaeus anahita Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021 (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Scotophaeus elburzensis Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021 (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Scytodes kumonga Zamani & Marusik, 2020 (Scytodidae) [[Iran](#), Oman, UAE]

Sestakovaia hyrcania Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Liocranidae) [[Iran](#)]

Shaitan angramainyu Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Sosticus montanus Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021 (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Spariolenus khoozestanus Zamani, 2016 (Sparassidae) [[Iran](#)]

Stemonyphantes arta Esyunin & Zamani, 2021 (Linyphiidae) [[Iran](#)]

Stemonyphantes verkana Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Linyphiidae) [[Iran](#)]

Synaphosus martinezi Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021 (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Tegenaria alamto Zamani, Marusik & Malek-Hosseini, 2018 (Agelenidae) [[Iran](#)]

Tegenaria arsacia Zamani & Marusik, 2019 (Agelenidae) [[Iran](#)]

Tegenaria daylamanica Zamani & Marusik, 2019 (Agelenidae) [[Iran](#)]

Tegenaria eros Zamani & Marusik, 2019 (Agelenidae) [[Iran](#)]

Tegenaria guseinovi Zamani & Marusik, 2019 (Agelenidae) [[Iran](#)]

Tegenaria rahnamayi Zamani & Marusik, 2019 (Agelenidae) [[Iran](#)]

Tegenaria shirin Zamani & Marusik, 2019 (Agelenidae) [[Iran](#)]

Theridion arsia Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Theridiidae) [[Iran](#)]

Trygetus cyrus Zamani & Marusik, 2022 (Zodariidae) [[Iran](#)]

Trygetus susianus Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Zodariidae) [[Iran](#)]

Uroctea gambronica Zamani & Bosselaers, 2020 (Oecobiidae) [[Iran](#)]

Zagrotus apophysalis Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021 (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Zagrotus bifurcatus [Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin & Marusik, 2021] (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Zagrotus borna Zamani & Marusik, 2021 (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Zagrottes parla Zamani & Marusik, 2021
(Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Zaitunia akhanii Marusik & Zamani, 2015
(Filistatidae) [[Iran](#)]

Zaitunia darreshurii Zamani & Marusik,
2018 (Filistatidae) [[Iran](#)]

Zaitunia vahabzadehi Zamani & Marusik,
2016 (Filistatidae) [[Iran](#)]

Zaitunia zagrosica Zamani & Marusik, 2018
(Filistatidae) [[Iran](#)]

Zelotes hyrcanus Zamani, Chatzaki, Esyunin
& Marusik, 2021 (Gnaphosidae) [[Iran](#)]

Zora huseynovi Zamani & Marusik, 2017
(Miturgidae) [[Iran](#)]